

MOTHER PROJECT

ACTIVITY BOOK

ABOUT MOTHER

It stands for **M**ultis**P**ecies **O**vary **T**issue **H**istology **E**lectronic **R**e**P**ository.
That probably doesn't make sense. Let's break it down!

Multispecies means that we study more than 1 kind of animal. We have studied monkeys, fish, hamsters, sheep, and more!

An **ovary** is an organ that females have so that they can make babies. **Tissue** is a group of cells that work together. At **MOTHER**, we study **Ovary Tissue**.

Histology is the science of cells and tissues. We use a microscope to study this.

An **electronic repository** is like an online library. At **MOTHER**, we collect images of cells using a microscope and put them into the electronic repository. Then anyone can access the images online!

61 to 70 of 915 Results

Sort

16418_UN_090a.ome.tif

Sep 30, 2022 - Zelinski Lab: Rhesus Macaque Ovary

TIFF Image - 620.3 MB - MD5: cc7...373

adult

Full Resolution Image

16418_UN_090a_reduced.tif

Sep 30, 2022 - Zelinski Lab: Rhesus Macaque Ovary

TIFF Image - 6.2 MB - MD5: dbf...cf9

adult

Reduced Image

16418_UN_090a_thumbnail.tif

Sep 30, 2022 - Zelinski Lab: Rhesus Macaque Ovary

TIFF Image - 256.0 KB - MD5: b64...21a

adult

Thumbnail Image

Crossword Puzzle!

ACROSS

1. tool used to magnify small things
3. the process of finding new knowledge
6. the study of cells and tissues

DOWN

2. a reproductive organ in females
4. a subject studied in school that has to do with observations and experiments
5. the smallest building block of life
6. a group of people that work together

Word Bank

Histology

Science

Ovary

Cells

Research

Team

Microscope

- 1 blue
- 2 grey
- 3 white
- 4 black
- 5 brown
- 6 pink

7 purple

Color By Number

Draw the other half

Color in the image after

This is a uterus and it is an organ in the female body where a baby grows! There are two ovaries, one on each side of the uterus. (It is the oval shaped organ that looks like it is being grabbed by a "hand").

Draw Yourself as a Researcher!

Sometimes scientists need to wear PPE (personal protective equipment) like goggles and lab coats

Rhesus Macaque

THEY ARE A TYPE OF MONKEY AND ONE OF MANY DIFFERENT SPECIES THAT WE STUDY. WHAT WE LEARN THROUGH THEM WILL BE ABLE TO BE USED FOR GIRLS AND WOMEN IN THE FUTURE. WITHOUT BEING ABLE TO STUDY ANIMALS LIKE THE RHESUS MACAQUES, OUR WORLD WOULD NOT BE THE SAME TODAY!

COLOR THEM IN!

If I were a scientist...

If I were a scientist, I would have _____ hair and be _____.

ADJECTIVE

ADJECTIVE

Before I do anything, I would wear my _____ to protect myself

CLOTHING ITEM

from any danger. Today I will be learning by using the scientific

method. First I need to make observations. My favorite thing to study

is _____ because it is _____. I will use a _____ to take a

NOUN

ADJECTIVE

NOUN

closer look at it. Next, I need to ask a question: How can I turn

_____ into _____? Then I need to make a hypothesis: If

NOUN

NOUN

_____ is mixed with _____, _____ and boiled, then it will

NOUN

COLOR

PLURAL NOUN

turn into _____. After that, I will create an experiment to see if

NOUN

my guess is true. I will use a _____ bowl to mix everything

SHAPE

_____ times. I will put it on a hot _____ to boil the mixture.

NUMBER

KITCHEN APPLIANCE

Once my experiment is done, I will make my conclusions. It turns out

that my guess was right! I am so _____ that this worked out. My

EMOTION

last step is to tell everyone else about what I did. I will use a _____

NOUN

to make a _____ poster to describe my experiment. I will present

ADJECTIVE

this to _____ people to share everything with them. I am so glad to

NUMBER

be a scientist to discover and learn new things everyday!

Wordsearch

Many of the words in this search are different types of ovarian follicles. Follicles are important because oocytes which are eggs, grow inside of follicles. Primordial follicles grow to become Primary follicles, which then grow to be Secondary follicles, which then grow to be Multilayer follicles and finally an Antral follicle! These follicles are way too small to be seen with our eyes, so we have to use a microscope to be able to see them.

T F T R R A U J S L I D E S Y
A O F E N S U O V A R I E S D
E F M Q J Y H Q P Y Y P R A Y
F W O P Y R J R R M I R S D G
W B Z L C I Y T I E E I R E O
S I S D L Z F W M Y X M E E L
C Y A K M I T R A S M O H S O
I N R T M U C L R W Y R T U T
O K I A X A I L Y U Y D O S S
G B Z U D T C E E F R I M E I
H Y I K L N Z A U E A A F H H
D M N U H H O X Q D J L Z R L
D W M M X J Q C P U T N F U U
U Q K Y O S T S E E E U E A B
M X L A R T N A K S N P G B W

Word Bank

- | | | | |
|------------|---------------|---------------|---------------|
| 1. mother | 4. multilayer | 7. slides | 10. secondary |
| 2. rhesus | 5. ovaries | 8. primordial | 11. histology |
| 3. macaque | 6. primary | 9. antral | 12. follicle |

Spot the Difference!

All but one is a primordial follicle. Find the transitional primordial follicle:

All but one is a primary follicle. Find the transitional primary follicle:

All but one is a secondary follicle. Find the multilayer follicle:

Wordsearch Answer Key

Word Bank

- | | | | |
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